

Spectrophotometric Determination of Ethylene Glycol in Motor Oil and Chocolate Package

MADHUSRI BHATTACHARJEE and V K GUPTA*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

Manuscript received 3 November 1993, revised 6 December 1994, accepted 1 February 1995

Several spectrophotometric methods have been reported for ethylene glycol¹⁻⁵. In the present investigation, a simple spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of ethylene glycol, which involves the oxidation of ethylene glycol with periodic acid to formaldehyde⁶ which on reaction with J-acid in presence of concentrated H₂SO₄ forms a yellow fluorescent dye⁷ having maximum absorbance at 470 nm.

Results and Discussion

The yellow fluorescent dye shows maximum absorbance at 470 nm, whereas the reagent blank shows no absorbance. The system obeys Beer's law over the concentration range 0.1–0.62 ppm of ethylene glycol. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be $22.0 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (± 100) and $0.0028 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation for seven determinations of 0.5 ppm were found to be ± 0.007 and 1.0% respectively. A 15 min heating time at 100° was sufficient for full colour development. Maximum colour was developed in concentrated H₂SO₄. A 0.2 ml of 0.005 M periodic acid was needed for complete conversion of ethylene glycol to formaldehyde⁶. The excess of periodic acid was removed with 0.2 ml of sodium arsenite solution. The minimum amount and concentration of J-acid required was 0.5 ml and 0.2% respectively. There was no significant change in absorbance value if excess of J-acid was added.

The effect of foreign species was studied by adding known amounts of foreign species to 10 $\mu\text{g}/20 \text{ ml}$ (0.5 ppm) of ethylene glycol prior to analysis. The method was found to be free from the interference of most of the organic compounds and inorganic ions. Compounds which on oxidation yield formaldehyde, e.g. methanol, interfere with the method. The tolerance limit (ppm) for the species are as follows : hydroxylamine (1500), *o*- and *p*-nitrophenol (1200); *m*-nitrophenol, pyridine, benzene (750); phenol, ethanol (600); CH₃COO⁻ (3000); SO₄²⁻ (2000); NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, HCO₃⁻, SiO₃²⁻ (1000); Fe³⁺ (800); Zn²⁺ (600); Mg²⁺, Cd²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺ (500). Formaldehyde and methanol showed positive interference.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched silica cell was used.

A stock solution containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ ethylene glycol was prepared in distilled water. A 0.005 M periodic acid solution was prepared in distilled water. A solution of J-acid (6-amino-1-naphthol-3-sulphonic acid) (250 mg) was prepared in concentrated H₂SO₄ (50 ml). Saturated solution of sodium bisulphite was freshly prepared in distilled water. All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : To aliquots containing 2–12.5 μg of ethylene glycol, periodic acid solution (0.2 ml) was added. The mixture was heated in a water-bath for 10 min at 50–60°. The solution was then cooled in an ice-bath and sodium bisulphite solution (0.2 ml) was added with constant shaking to decolourise the excess iodine. The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 min. The contents were placed in an ice-bath and to it J-acid solution (0.5 ml) was added. It was then heated on a boiling water-bath for 20 min. The mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and the volume made upto 20 ml with concentrated H₂SO₄. A yellow fluorescent dye was obtained, having maximum absorbance at 470 nm.

Applications : The method was applied for the detection of ethylene glycol present in chocolate wrappers and motor oil.

Ethylene glycol is reported to be present in detectable concentration in chocolate wrappers⁸. The wrapper of chocolate was dipped in distilled water (25 ml), allowed to

stand for 30 min and then washed with distilled water (20 ml) and filtered. Aliquot (1 ml) of the filtrate was tested by the above method after spiking with known amounts of ethylene glycol. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF ETHYLENE GLYCOL IN CHOCOLATE WRAPPERS AND USED MOTOR OIL*

Sl. no.	Sample	Amount of ethylene glycol (μg)		Recovery %
		Added	Found	
Volume of extract = 1 ml				
1.	Chocolate Wrappers			
	S ₁	10	10.20	102.0
	S ₂	5	5.15	103.0
	S ₃	10	10.05	100.5
	S ₄	5	5.25	105.0
2.	Motor oil			
	S ₁	5	5.10	102.0
	S ₂	10	10.20	102.0
	S ₃	5	5.20	104.0
	S ₄	10	10.15	101.5

* Mean of three repetitive analyses.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED METHOD WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Sl. no.	Reagent	λ_{max} nm	Beer's law range (ppm)	Remarks
1.	Chromotropic acid ^d	575	2–8	Less sensitive
2.	3-Methylbenzothiazolin-2-one hydrazone ^b	630	15–125	Reagent not easily available
3.	Amodiaquine dihydrochloride ^c	442	10–60	Less sensitive
4.	6-Amino-1-naphthol-3-sulphonic acid ^d	470	0.1–0.62	Sensitive and stable

^aRef. 3. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 5. ^dPresent method

Ethylene glycol is found to be present in used motor oil². The present method was also applied for the determination of trace amounts of ethylene glycol in used motor

oil. To the oil sample (0.5 g), distilled water (15 ml) was added and the mixture was shaken well for dissolving ethylene glycol in water. The reaction mixture was then heated at 60–70° to ensure complete dissolution and allowed to stand for 1 h. It was filtered to separate the oil. The container was washed with distilled water (5 ml). Aliquot (1 ml) of the filtrate was tested by the above method after spiking with known amounts of ethylene glycol. The results are presented in Table 1.

The proposed method is simple, sensitive, free from interference and highly selective. The yellow fluorescent dye is stable for more than 24 h. The method has been compared with other spectrophotometric methods and found to be quite sensitive (Table 2).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, for facilities. One of the authors (M.B.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for granting a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. M. SRIVANASAN and S. THIAGARAJAN, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **282**, 143.
2. M. W. SCOGGINS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1977, **49**, 582.
3. SHIGERU INGARASHI, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1980, **29**, 150 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1980, **39**, 4C20).
4. J. URBANSKI and E. KEDZIERSKA, *Chem. Anal.*, 1976, **21**, 509 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1977, **32**, 2H87).
5. K. K. VERMA, D. GUPTA, S. K. SANGHI and A. JAIN, *Analyst (London)*, 1987, **112**, 1519.
6. G. ZWEIG, "Analytical Methods for Pesticides Plant Growth Regulators and Food Additives", Academic, New York, 1964, pp. 217–20.
7. E. SAWICKI, T. R. HAUSER and S. MEPHERSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 1460.
8. L. CASTLE, H. R. CLOKE, J. R. STARTIN and J. GILLBERT, *J. Assoc. Anal. Chem.*, 1988, **71**, 449.

